

READING ACTIVITY AND READING CULTURE

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Annotation: This article talked about reading activities and reading culture, educational significance of the book.

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The relevance of developing theoretical and practical foundations for guiding reading activity is explained by the obvious fact that it is possible to develop the ability to fully read only by relying on meaningful and processed experience in studying the phenomenon of reading. Let's start traditionally, with the definition of concepts.

Reading activity (along with reader consciousness and reader communication) is a way of human existence, one of the spheres of manifestation of reading culture. It accumulates and implements one's own reading experience and experience of interaction with other readers, and the emotional and intellectual development of the individual occurs.

The regulator of this activity, the means of its experience, cognition and evaluation is the reader's consciousness - "the highest form of reflection of the reader's reality, the reader's world". The reader not only perceives, cognizes, experiences and evaluates what he read, but also refracts it in his consciousness in accordance with various personal and social needs, and then applies what he has received in other types of life activities (professional, leisure, family, etc.).

The special nature of verbal creativity, in the development of which the mind, feelings, and imagination participate, is due to the fact that reading activity consists of aesthetic, cognitive and mental. Literature has a powerful emotional impact and provides intellectual and sometimes sensual pleasure. If the content of a scientific truth or even a moral doctrine is assimilated directly by the mind, then the content of a work of verbal creativity must be experienced in order to be understood. Without aesthetic, figurative perception, it is impossible to comprehend a literary text, since it must be accompanied by an interested emotional-personal reaction.

Without love for a book, neither knowledge nor comprehension of the values inherent in it is possible. Modern rational society, unfortunately, underestimates the importance of improving human sensuality. Meanwhile, the history of the life of humanity and each individual clearly shows that very, very

much in life is determined and decided at the level of sensory, aesthetic, and not logical interactions.

More Zh.-Zh. Rousseau remarked, “only a thinking man is just a spoiled animal”. It is emotional experience that constitutes a special sphere of a person’s spiritual life, and the level of emotional receptivity determines both the degree of intellectual development and the moral guidelines of a person. “The emotional principle permeates all sides of the human self, it cannot be separated from either the character of a person, nor from his behavior, nor from his attitude to the world and, consequently, to books and reading”.

Educational influence is one of the most socially significant moments in the existence of art, therefore it is an integral part of a system of social institutions designed to form the ideological attitudes of a person, the content of her ideals, value — orientate a person, bringing him as close as possible to the values of society.

The educational value of works of art and literature was realized in antiquity. It is only important not to narrow this meaning, not to understand it simplistically, as the fulfillment of some specific didactic task.

Most often, in the educational function of art, the emphasis is on the fact that it teaches to imitate positive characters or encourages a person to take certain specific actions. According to some critics, a positive literary hero must necessarily be a role model. This formulation of the question leads to vulgarization and greatly simplifies the role of literature, and the work as a whole acquires a pronounced didactic character.

Reading is not only a source of aesthetic and intellectual enjoyment, but also one of the ways to explore the world. Literature promotes natural immersion in the native language, reveals its secrets. Each literary work is in one way or another a fragment of the “encyclopedia of life”. Along with other types of art, but much more actively, their literature purposefully creates a chronicle of the historical life of the nation, produces and forms an ideology, and carries out continuity between generations. With the help of literature, a person is able to learn such things about himself and about the world, which he would not have learned with the help of the most accurate and rigorous science.

The culture of reading is the ability to perceive a work in all its depth and integrity, understanding it as a unique intermediary between the author and the reader. To master the culture of reading means to learn to understand the author, and to realize the process of reading itself as a dialogue, a special kind of communication, a conversation between the author and the reader.

References:

1. Асмус В.Ф. Вопросы теории и истории эстетики: сборник статей / В.Ф. Асмус. — М.: Искусство, 1968. — С. 44.
2. Барт Р. Избр. работы. Семиотика. Поэтика / Р. Барт. — М., 1994. — С. 375.
3. Белинский В.Г. Полное собрание сочинений Д.И. Фонвизина... // Белинский В.Г. Собрание сочинений: в 9 т.— Т. 2. — М.: Художественная литература, 1976. — С. 95.
4. Бородина В.А. Читательское развитие личности: теоретико-методологические аспекты: автореферат диссертации ... д-ра пед. наук / В.А. Бородина. — СПб.: СПбГУК, 2007. — С. 14, 24.
5. Лотман Ю.М. Культура и взрыв // Ю.М. Лотман. Семиосфера. — СПб.: Искусство-СПБ, 2001. — С. 129.

